

LIBRARY AUTOMATION: A STUDY OF MEDICAL LIBRARIES IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study investigates the use of automation systems in libraries of medical institutes across Punjab. A quantitative research design was employed using a structured survey questionnaire, which was disseminated to 71 medical libraries across Punjab. The collected data was analyzed through SPSS-25. The findings reveal that the majority of the medical libraries in Punjab were fully automated. Most libraries have opted free and open-source library software such as Koha and LIMS. Overall, the majority of respondents reported satisfaction with modules related to circulation, cataloging, reporting, administration, and user management, particularly noting the ease of use, installation and backup operations. However, several challenges were also identified, including insufficient library budgets, inadequate internet connectivity, limited institutional support, lack of technical assistance and consulting services, and a shortage of training opportunities for library staff.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in the global flow of information presents significant challenges for library professionals, particularly in managing resources in a manner that ensures timely and efficient access to information. The primary objective of Library and Information Science (LIS) professionals is to fulfill users' information needs by ensuring access to credible and reliable sources. Libraries play a critical role in supporting students and researchers with accurate and authoritative information. In traditional library environments, users often spend a considerable amount of time locating needed materials, frequently relying on the assistance of library staff. The emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has transformed this landscape, enabling libraries to streamline their operations and

significantly reduce search time for users and workload for librarians. As we navigate an information society, the rapid growth of digital content and ongoing advancements in ICT have underscored the importance of library automation software especially within academic institutions (Verma, 2014). Medical libraries, in particular, contain rare and specialized resources in the field of health sciences. The automation of these libraries is essential for managing collections and services effectively. As Siddique and Mehmood (2015) assert, library automation software has considerably improved the efficiency of critical library functions such as cataloging, circulation, acquisitions, booking, online catalog access, and serials management when compared to manual systems. Moreover, automation reduces the need

for extensive staff involvement and minimizes the time users spend searching for resources.

Library automation refers to the use of computers and related technology (e.g., scanners and printers) to perform essential library functions such as acquisition, cataloging, classification, circulation, and serial control. By integrating ICT tools into library operations, automation enhances service efficiency and reduces manual workload, leading to improved performance and service delivery (Komolafe & Ojo, 2019). The history of library automation dates back to the 1960s, and Borgman (1997) categorizes this evolution into three key phases:

The initial focus of automation was on streamlining internal library workflows. As higher education expanded and library collections grew in the 1960s and 1970s, it became evident that manual systems were no longer sufficient. Automation allowed for faster data processing, and initial efforts were aimed at computerizing core functions such as circulation, cataloging, acquisitions, and serials management. A major milestone was the development of the Machine Readable Cataloging (MARC) format by the Library of Congress in 1966. Shared catalogs and networks like RLIN and WLN (introduced by OCLC) significantly reduced duplication of effort and improved access.

During the 1980s, libraries began employing Integrated Library Systems (ILS), which enabled online ordering, record management, and automated circulation services. Local area networks and online public access catalogs (OPACs) emerged, initially available only within library premises but eventually accessible via the internet by the end of the decade.

This phase saw the development of union catalogs and expanded internet access. Protocols such as Z39.50 enabled online data sharing across institutions. Cloud computing further transformed library software, allowing web-based access and collaborative cataloging across platforms.

In Pakistan, while computers were introduced in libraries as early as the 1960s, significant focus on automation emerged in the 1990s. The Pakistan Scientific and Technological Information Centre

(PASTIC) was among the first to use computers to compile a union catalog for scientific periodicals (Haider, 1998). However, limited funding restricted widespread adoption of automation technologies during this period. Prominent early adopters included the National Agricultural Research Center (NARC), Aga Khan University (AKU), and Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS). The Netherlands Library Development Project (NLDP), as noted by Mahmood (1999), played a pivotal role in introducing modern technologies in Pakistani libraries. Support from international organizations such as WHO, UNESCO, IAEA, and FAO also contributed to the development of automated systems. From 2000 to 2010, automation became more common, with locally developed systems like the Library Information Management System (LIMS) used particularly in college libraries. After 2010, open-source systems like Koha gained popularity due to their compliance with library standards and cost-effectiveness (Asim, 2017).

Several studies have documented the evolution of library software usage in Pakistan. Ahmad (1993) found that 95 libraries in Rawalpindi and Islamabad were using computers mainly for acquisitions and cataloging. Sadiq (1994) reported that 23 libraries were using CDS/ISIS software. The Pakistan Library Automation Group (2005) noted that 50 libraries across Pakistan and the Middle East had adopted automation software. Shafique and Mahmood (2008) found that libraries in Lahore commonly used INMAGIC, LAMP, WINISIS, and LIMS. Ullah et al. (2011) found that 8 out of 16 medical libraries in Lahore were automated, while Mairaj and El-Hadi (2012) reported that 16 medical libraries had adopted automation software. Asim (2017) found that 22 universities in Punjab used Koha, and Naveed (2018) confirmed the increasing use of Koha and LIMS in HEC-recognized universities and DAIs.

Problem Statement

In today's digital era, library automation is not optional it is essential. While libraries globally are leveraging software solutions for automation to improve efficiency and accessibility (Ajani &

Buraimo, 2022), many medical libraries in Punjab still rely on manual systems for core functions such as cataloging and circulation. This manual approach impedes quick access to information and hinders resource sharing. With the exponential growth of medical knowledge and the digitization of scholarly content, there is an urgent need for medical libraries to adopt and implement effective automation systems. This study addresses this critical gap by exploring the current use of library automation software in Punjab's medical libraries, identifying challenges faced by librarians, assessing satisfaction with existing systems, and recommending improvements. Although various studies have explored library automation in Pakistan, none have specifically examined its implementation in the medical libraries of Punjab.

Research Objectives (ROs)

RO1- To identify the name of the library software being used in medical libraries

RO2 - To identify the purposes of using library automation software in medical libraries

RO3 - To examine the problems faced by librarians while using library software and,

RO4 - To assess the satisfaction level of librarians with the features of the automation software used.

Literature Review

A growing body of literature has explored the purposes for which libraries adopt automation software. Iqbal et al. (2023), in their study of Sialkot libraries, found that library software was primarily introduced to enhance efficiency and streamline operations, though challenges such as inadequate technical support were reported. Similarly, Choi and Pruett (2019) identified cost-effectiveness and improved technological capacity as major motivations behind the adoption of open-source software (OSS) in U.S. academic libraries. Studies across developing contexts echo these findings. Ukachi et al. (2014) and Ngozi et al. (2014) emphasized the role of OSS in reducing staff workload, facilitating remote access, and empowering libraries to customize systems to local needs. In Nigerian university libraries, Komolafe-Opadeji and Ojo (2019) as well as Ajani and

Buraimo (2022) highlighted the positive impact of automation on cataloging, resource access, and overall service delivery, despite persistent infrastructural challenges. Likewise, Uzomba et al. (2015) and Ahammad (2014) reported increasing adoption of Koha due to its usability and functionality. Other regional studies confirm similar patterns. Ponelis and Adoma (2018) noted higher OSS adoption in private Ugandan universities compared to public ones, while financial and human resource constraints limited implementation. Collectively, these findings suggest that libraries across contexts adopt automation primarily to improve efficiency, enhance access, reduce staff workload, and expand service delivery though the pace and scope of adoption vary according to institutional resources and local challenges. Despite the clear benefits, numerous studies highlight persistent challenges in the adoption and effective utilization of library automation systems. Alam (2017), in Bangladesh, identified limited technical expertise, insufficient funding, and weak IT infrastructure as major barriers to the adoption of open-source integrated library systems (OSLIS). Similarly, Yadav and Rajput (2022) documented obstacles in Indian college libraries, including inadequate internet access, data entry errors, and financial constraints. In the African context, Kari and Baro (2014) and Otunla (2016) noted recurring problems such as lack of skilled staff, unreliable power supply, and staff resistance. Jasimudeen et al. (2012) added that data migration and administrative approval were particular hurdles in the Indian subcontinent. Other studies stress the importance of ongoing training, as Das and Chatterjee (2015) and Mirza and Arif (2016) argued that professional development is critical to overcome skill gaps among library professionals. Research in Pakistan by Rafiq and Ameen (2009) highlighted broader systemic challenges such as the digital divide and social inequities, which slow the adoption of open-source systems. Similarly, Rajput and Jain (2006) and Rajput and Gautam (2010) found that inadequate administrative support and a lack of trained staff limited automation progress in Indian special libraries. Taken together, the literature suggests that while libraries recognize the

necessity of automation, they often face structural, financial, and human resource barriers that hinder full-scale implementation. A number of studies have examined satisfaction levels with integrated library systems (ILS). Alam and Islam (2021), studying public university libraries in Bangladesh, found that advanced features such as OPAC, automated circulation, and email alerts were highly valued, though some users lacked awareness of available services. Similarly, Gohain and Saikia (2013) reported high student satisfaction with OPAC services in India, emphasizing the importance of training to maximize benefits. Evidence from Pakistan aligns with these findings. Asim and Miraj (2019) reported that library professionals in Punjab expressed overall satisfaction with Koha, particularly with circulation and cataloging modules, though acquisition and serials management remained areas of concern. Iqbal et al. (2023) also found that librarians in Sialkot valued user-friendly features and multilingual support. Comparative studies across regions show similar trends. Jasimudeen et al. (2012) and Akpokodje (2015) found that the majority of librarians and users expressed satisfaction with Koha's usability, though challenges in maintenance and advanced customization persisted. Khan and Aysha (2022) confirmed that most librarians appreciated features such as Web OPAC, data backup, and overall ease of use. Overall, the literature indicates that satisfaction levels are generally high, especially with open-source systems like Koha, though certain modules and infrastructural limitations continue to affect full user acceptance.

Library Automation in the context of Developing Countries

Kabir Khan and Sheikh (2022) employed a survey approach to investigate the prevalent open source software (OSS) use at Islamabad's university libraries for the improvement of Institutional Repositories (IRs). Their findings revealed a higher propensity among libraries to adopt open source software over local or commercial alternatives. Additionally, they highlighted several significant challenges that librarians encounter when employing software for open-source

institutional repositories. Among these difficulties were finding appropriate software and digitization materials, inadequate parent organization support, a lack of training opportunities, and a staffing shortfall. Khan et al. (2016) discussed the detailed procedure of enactment of Koha in the Government College University (GCU) Lahore libraries, as well as data migration from LMS. The study concluded that the LMS software was not Unicode or MARC-based software, and the Urdu typeface was not supported. The GCU libraries held around 100,000 Urdu language literary works. In light of this, the library staff decided at a meeting to implement the Koha ILS software. Sadique and Mehmood (2015) examined the usage of library software in Pakistani libraries. This research, based on a literature review, disclosed that the use of automation software in Pakistani libraries was not satisfactory compared to advanced countries. Naveed et al. (2021) presented a quantitative study to explore the current state of library management systems utilized in libraries of Lahore. They noted that the library management systems in Lahore were utilized by 33 recognized universities and degree-awarding institute libraries of HEC, and these systems generally met librarians' expectations. Midrar Ullah et al. (2011) found that eight medical university libraries in Lahore out of sixteen had adopted LMS. A case study of six legislative assembly libraries in Pakistan described data migration from LAMP to Koha using MarcEdit software. The study concluded that primary obstacles to OSS adoption included a lack of funds, inexperienced employees, and a lack of interest among technical associations, though OSS was still adopted due to its affordability (Shafi Ullah and Qutab, 2012). Farzana and Mehmood (2008) found INMAGIC to be the most favored software among Lahore librarians due to ease of use and support. However, WINISIS and LAMP were also popular, though with limited functionalities. Siddique and Mehmood (2015) reported that both public and private university libraries in Pakistan used software such as LIMS, KOHA, VIRTUA, and WINISIS, with open-source options often chosen due to lack of funding. Rafiq (2009) extended this discussion

globally, showing that librarians from developing countries demonstrated more hesitancy toward OSS compared to their counterparts in developed nations. Islam et al. (2019) investigated the use of Koha in Bangladeshi medical libraries, finding that only three of 24 libraries had adopted it, with most unaware of automation systems. Similarly, Fingillah and Aliero (2023) reported that Kebbi State's academic libraries in Nigeria were only partially automated, citing lack of funding, skilled staff, and infrastructure as the major constraints. Olagoke and Kolawole (2019), however, found that private universities in Southwest Nigeria had largely automated, improving librarian performance and service quality. Alam and Mezbah-ul-Islam (2019) identified affordability, backup systems, and open-source availability as primary factors influencing OSILS adoption in Bangladeshi university libraries. Georgina and Nicholas (2021) also found Koha to be the most widely used in Nigerian tertiary institutions, though funding and ICT training were challenges.

Library Automation in the context of Developed Countries

In contrast, libraries in developed countries report higher levels of automation, though they too face challenges related to cost, upgrades, and staff training. In India, Kuri (2022) and Naveen and Nagesh (2016) found that automation levels were higher in well-funded institutions, but some colleges still lagged due to financial and infrastructural issues. Farahi and Gandhi (2011) highlighted similar trends in medical libraries in Iran and Karnataka, where automation existed but was not always comprehensive. Madhusudhan and Singh (2016) compared Virtua, Libsys, NewGenLib, and Koha, noting that commercial systems generally offered more advanced functionalities, though open-source alternatives were gaining traction. Breeding (2015) similarly observed global growth in Koha and other OSS, even in developed countries, though proprietary systems like Alma and Sierra retained dominance in larger institutions. Choi (2021) found that in U.S. public libraries, open-source adoption was slowed by compatibility issues and lack of awareness. Sharma and Kandari (2021) reported

that in India's technical institutions, automation significantly improved user satisfaction, despite ICT skill gaps among staff. In China and Kuwait, the situation reflects a preference for commercial or locally developed systems. Jabeen et al. (2018) found that Chinese libraries favored commercial software due to perceived risks with open-source systems, while Ansari (2011) reported that in Kuwait, most special libraries were automated but still relied on traditional practices because of insufficient skilled staff. Corral and Jolly (2019) documented that in U.K. academic libraries, strategic digital planning often accompanied automation, but staff training gaps persisted. Luo and Qin (2017) highlighted that Chinese university libraries faced challenges in aligning automation with broader digital ecosystems. Taken together, the literature shows that developed countries enjoy a higher rate of automation adoption, but they also encounter issues of cost, staff competence, and system upgrades. The contrast with developing countries is not absolute, but libraries in resource-rich contexts are generally better positioned to sustain long-term automation (IFLA, 2015).

Types of Library Automation Software

Open-source software (OSS) refers to programs whose source code is freely available for use, modification, and redistribution. In the library context, OSS has gained global traction due to its flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and community-driven innovation (Rafiq & Ameen, 2009). Ukachi et al. (2014) categorized library automation software into two types: open-source and proprietary. Uzomba et al. (2015), in their study of Nigerian university libraries, noted that OSS has become increasingly prominent with the rise of internet-based collaboration and free software development. Popular OSS solutions in library automation include: Koha ILS, LIMS, NewGenLib, Evergreen, OpenBiblio, BiblioteQ and PHPMyLibrary.

Proprietary (or commercial) software refers to licensed systems owned by developers or corporations, where source code access and modifications are restricted. Mahmood (1996) noted that commercial library software packages

are often supported by extensive documentation and user guides, enabling librarians to make informed choices. Malwad (1995) further emphasized that commercial solutions are typically robust, user-friendly, and reliable, as they are developed for competitive markets with broad client bases. Notable examples include: Virtua, Insignia Library System, Libsys, Destiny Library Manager and MIDAS Library Management System.

Methodology

This study employed a **quantitative, survey-based design** to examine the use of library automation software in medical libraries across Punjab, Pakistan. The methodology included defining the research approach, population, measurement instruments, data collection procedures, and analysis techniques. Given the objectives of the study, a **quantitative research approach** was adopted. As noted by Muijs (2011), quantitative methods enable the systematic collection and statistical analysis of data from large populations, making them suitable for exploring perceptions, behaviors, and practices (Creswell, 2011). A **survey design** was selected to capture data from geographically dispersed respondents, a method widely used for assessing attitudes, practices, and current conditions (Gay et al., 2009). The study population comprised **71 medical libraries** affiliated with Higher Education Commission (HEC)-recognized universities, colleges, and degree-awarding institutes in Punjab, including both public and private institutions. Because of the relatively small population, a **census technique** was employed, incorporating all 71 libraries (Creswell, 2010). Data were collected using a **structured online questionnaire**, developed in Google Forms and distributed via email and WhatsApp. The instrument consisted of three sections: **Section A**, Demographic information (e.g., designation, type of institution, qualification, experience). **Section B**, General information on the use of library software (e.g., software name and type). **Section C**, Items measuring the purposes of automation, problems encountered, and satisfaction with features.

The main construct, **automation software**, was measured using a **55-item scale** adapted from Shakeel and Aysha (2022) and revised by Iqbal et al. (2023). Responses were recorded on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from *Strongly Disagree* (1) to *Strongly Agree* (5) for adoption-related items, and *Highly Dissatisfied* (1) to *Highly Satisfied* (5) for satisfaction-related items. Instrument reliability was confirmed using **Cronbach's Alpha**, which produced a value of **0.883**, indicating high internal consistency across the items. A list of medical libraries was obtained from official university and HEC websites. The questionnaire link was sent to library professionals via email and WhatsApp. Out of 71 distributed questionnaires, **65 valid responses** were received, yielding a **91% response rate**. The data were downloaded from Google Forms, coded, and analyzed using **SPSS version 27**. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were used to summarize the data.

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Data were collected from **65 medical libraries** across Punjab, Pakistan. Of these, **44 respondents (67.7%)** were affiliated with private institutions, while **21 (32.3%)** represented public sector libraries. Regarding gender, **41 respondents (63.1%)** were male and **24 (36.9%)** were female. The age distribution showed that the largest group, **23 respondents (35.4%)**, were between 31–35 years old. A further **14 (21.5%)** were aged 36–40, **19 (29.2%)** were above 40, **7 (10.8%)** were 26–30, and only **2 (3.1%)** were under 25 years old. In terms of educational qualifications, nearly half of the respondents, **31 (47.7%)**, held a Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) degree. **29 (44.6%)** had MPhil degrees in LIS, **3 (4.6%)** had PhDs, and **2 (3.1%)** reported holding other qualifications (e.g., BS in LIS). Professional experience varied: **22 respondents (33.8%)** had 11–15 years of service, **18 (27.7%)** had 6–10 years, **10 (15.4%)** each had 1–5 years and 16–20 years, while only **5 (7.7%)** reported more than 20 years of experience. With respect to designation, the

largest group were librarians (33; 50.8%), followed by chief librarians (13; 20%), senior librarians (10; 15.4%), assistant librarians (4; 6.2%), and deputy librarians (3; 4.6%). Overall, the sample

reflects a diverse distribution of demographic and professional characteristics, with the majority being mid-career librarians working in private sector institutions.

Table 1
Demographic Information (N=65)

Variables		F	(%)
Gender	Male	41	63.1
	Female	24	36.9
Age	20-25	2	3.1
	26-30	7	10.8
	31-35	23	35.4
	35-40	14	21.5
	Over 40	19	29.2
	Type of University	From Public	21
	From Private	44	67.7
Academic Qualification	MLIS	31	47.7
	M.Phil.	29	44.6
	PhD	3	4.6
	Any other	2	3.1
Professional Experience	1-5	10	15.4
	6-10	18	27.7
	11-15	22	33.8
	16-20	10	15.4
	Over 20	5	7.7
	Designation	Chief Librarian	13
Deputy Librarian		3	4.6
Senior Librarian		10	15.4
Librarian		34	52.3
Assistant Librarian		4	6.2
Any Other (please specify)		1	1.5
Total		65	100.0

RO1- Name of the library software being used in medical libraries

The outcomes show that the maximum of the libraries (30, 46.2%) were using Koha ILS. A

large number of libraries, 20 (30.8%), were using LIMS for automation, while 1 (1.5%) respondents were using Virtua software, and 14 (21.1%) respondents were using any other software for automation.

Table 2

Name of library software being used in medical libraries (N=65)

Library software	Frequency	Percent
Koha ILS	30	46.2
Virtua	1	1.5
LIMS	20	30.8
Any Other (Please specify)	14	21.5
Total	65	100.0

RO2 - Purposes of using library automation software in medical libraries

The results presented in Table 4.5 highlight the major factors influencing the adoption of library automation software in medical libraries. The highest-rated determinants were the reputation of the software within the professional community ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.889$) and the availability of multilingual support ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.717$). These findings suggest that professional endorsement and inclusivity in terms of language remain central to decision-making, reflecting librarians' preference for systems that are both trusted and accessible to diverse user groups. Equally significant were features directly tied to functionality and efficiency. Respondents strongly emphasized the importance of a web OPAC ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 1.05$), support for the MARC21 cataloging standard ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.926$), and the ease of installation ($M = 3.92$, $SD = 0.989$). Together, these findings reinforce the role of international standards and usability in ensuring interoperability and smooth implementation of automation systems. The endorsement of free availability, hosting, and

support facilities ($M = 3.97$, $SD = 0.809$) also reflects the budgetary realities of medical libraries in Punjab, where resource constraints make open-source and cost-effective solutions particularly attractive. Related to this, respondents acknowledged the significance of economic feasibility ($M = 3.82$, $SD = 0.998$), suggesting that cost-effectiveness is a critical driver of adoption, consistent with findings from developing countries where budgetary support for libraries is often limited (Rafiq, 2009; Singh & Sanaman, 2012). Other positively rated features, such as Library 2.0 tools ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.808$), discovery services ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 0.626$), and copy cataloging through Z39.50 ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 1.068$), indicate growing recognition of user-centered services and integration capabilities in modern library environments. Although these features received slightly lower ratings, their mean scores still demonstrate overall agreement regarding their value. Taken together, these findings indicate that medical libraries prioritize reputation, multilingual accessibility, standards compliance, affordability, and user-oriented services when adopting automation software.

Table 3

Purposes of using library software for library automation (N=65)

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Availability of required features	3.97	1.060
Free availability of software	3.97	1.060
Easy installation process	3.92	.989

Economic cost of implementation and maintenance	3.82	.998
Hosting and support services for software are easily available	3.97	.809
Provision of discovery features	3.831	.626
Popularity of the software among the profession's community	4.08	.889
Software provides search facility for copy cataloguing through Z39.50	3.78	1.068
Software provides multilingual support	4.05	.717
Software supports MARC21 standard for cataloguing	3.95	.926
Availability of Library 2.0 features	3.86	.808
Availability of web OPAC	3.98	1.053

Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Undecided, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree

RO3 - Problems Faced by librarians while using library software and,

The results in Table 4 reveal that respondents rated all 16 potential problems associated with library automation software above the neutral point ($M > 3.02$), which indicates a general consensus that significant challenges persist despite widespread adoption of automation. This finding underscores that while automation software has become integral to medical libraries in Punjab, its implementation is not without operational and technical obstacles. The elevated mean scores suggest recurring issues such as insufficient funding, limited internet connectivity, lack of training opportunities, and inadequate institutional support, as identified in earlier sections of this study. These challenges align with prior research, which highlights financial constraints, infrastructure deficiencies, and inadequate human resource capacity as persistent barriers to successful library automation,

particularly in developing countries (Rafiq, 2009). Moreover, technical concerns such as limited upgradation facilities, lack of consultancy and technical services, and restricted administrative rights managed by IT departments further hinder the effective utilization of automation software. Similar findings have been reported in study conducted in African context, where libraries often rely on external vendors or IT units, leading to delays in system customization and reduced autonomy for library staff (Singh & Sanaman, 2012). Taken together, these findings suggest a paradox: although medical libraries in Punjab are increasingly adopting automation to enhance efficiency and user services, unresolved financial, infrastructural, and technical issues threaten the sustainability and long-term success of automation initiatives. Addressing these problems through targeted training programs, adequate budgeting, and stronger institutional cooperation will be crucial for ensuring that the benefits of library automation software are fully realized.

Table 4: Problems faced while using library automation software (N=65)

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Non-cooperation in library automation by University / Institution	3.15	1.135
Lack of consultancy and technical services	3.15	1.135
Lack of competency and willingness of library staff	3.03	1.145
Availability of training facilities	3.28	1.179
Inadequate library budget	3.48	.970
Lack of customization facility	3.26	.989

Lack of up gradation facility	3.33	1.085
Lack of IT infrastructure facilities (Hardware /Software)	3.06	1.171
Lack of admin right by IT department	3.11	1.147
Lack of admin right for software-by-software house / company	3.02	1.111
Lack of library automation policy	3.08	1.279
Staff transfer	3.09	1.195
No cooperation among super ordinate with subordinates	2.91	1.071
Lack of fund / economic resources	3.34	1.122
Compliance with internet	3.28	1.206
Lack of admin right by IT department	3.28	1.206

Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Undecided, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree

RO4 - Satisfaction level of librarians with the features of the automation software used.

The findings presented in Table 5 demonstrate that respondents expressed a generally high level of satisfaction with the features of library automation software used in medical libraries across Punjab. The circulation module (M = 4.23, SD = 0.679), ease of use (M = 4.17, SD = 0.802), and cataloguing module (M = 4.08, SD = 0.777) emerged as the most highly rated features, indicating that the core functional aspects of automation software are effectively meeting the day-to-day operational needs of libraries. This is consistent with earlier research which emphasizes that circulation and cataloguing modules form the backbone of library management systems, directly influencing user services and workflow efficiency (Jasimudeen et al. 2012). In addition to core functionalities, respondents also expressed satisfaction with modules supporting user engagement and administrative efficiency. Patron modules (M = 4.05, SD = 0.717), affordability and ease of installation (M = 3.98, SD = 0.599), reporting and administration modules (M = 3.98, SD = 0.599), and backup facilities (M = 3.97, SD = 0.749) were all positively evaluated. This suggests that medical libraries value not only operational modules but also those that reduce administrative burden and ensure cost-effectiveness and sustainability. Similar study corroborate these

findings, indicating that affordability and ease of maintenance are major determinants in the adoption of open-source software like Koha in resource-constrained institutions (Rafiq, 2009). Furthermore, the relatively high satisfaction with user-centered features such as Web OPAC (M = 3.94, SD = 0.916), new arrivals display (M = 3.92, SD = 0.735), and data transfer to newer versions (M = 3.91, SD = 0.785) demonstrates that libraries recognize the importance of accessibility and continuous service improvement. These features contribute to enhancing the user experience, promoting transparency, and ensuring that libraries remain current with evolving technological needs. Prior literature similarly underscores the importance of web-based access and discoverability as essential components of modern library services (Bhatti, 2013). Taken together, these findings indicate that medical libraries in Punjab are broadly satisfied with their automation systems, particularly valuing modules that ensure efficiency, ease of use, affordability, and enhanced user access. The corroboration with existing literature suggests that the positive perception of automation software is not unique to this context but reflects broader trends in academic libraries, especially in developing countries where resource optimization and user-centered service delivery are critical priorities.

Table 5*Satisfaction level with the features of library software (N=65)*

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Price wise affordability	3.98	.599
Easy installation	3.98	.599
Easy to use	4.17	.802
Online help	3.78	.875
Maintenance and support	3.69	.828
Acquisition Modules	3.86	.726
Cataloguing Modules	4.08	.777
Circulation Modules	4.23	.679
Multi-lingual facility	3.88	.801
Patron Modules (Membership)	4.05	.717
Serials Modules	3.63	.894
Reports Modules	3.98	.780
Administration Modules	3.98	.760
Web OPAC	3.94	.916
Customization	3.77	.897
Easily accessible from anywhere through internet	3.75	.969
Easy backup facility	3.97	.749
Easy data transfer to latest version	3.91	.785
Can manage more than one library at one time	3.92	.735
Collection may be transferred from one library to another library easily through software	3.71	.861
ILL facility	3.55	.791
New arrivals display facility	3.92	.714

Scale: 1=Highly Dissatisfied, 2=Dissatisfied, 3=No Opinion, 4=Satisfied, 5=Highly Satisfied

Discussion

The analyses demonstrated that the Koha library management software was the most widely adopted system compared to LIMS and Virtua. A few respondents reported using other software, though they did not specify the names. These findings are consistent with the study of Asim and Mairaj (2019), who concluded that Koha ILS adoption in university libraries of Punjab is increasing due to its web OPAC facility, free availability, and support for both MARC21 and Z39.50 standards. The present study also confirmed that the majority of medical libraries were using free and open-source software for automation. The study was to determine the purpose of using library software in medical libraries of Punjab. The results showed that libraries adopted software for several reasons, including popularity among the professional community, multilingual support, availability of

essential features, compliance with MARC21 standards, and the provision of Z39.50 search facilities for copy cataloguing. Respondents also valued the availability of web OPAC, free access, and Library 2.0 features. These findings align with Iqbal et al. (2023), who reported similar adoption reasons in academic libraries of Sialkot, emphasizing free availability and required features. Ukachi et al. (2014) also confirmed that academic libraries adopted automation software due to its efficiency. Likewise, Naveed et al. (2021) highlighted that the accessibility of required modules and customization potential led to wider adoption of LIMS, while Asim and Mairaj (2019) observed Koha's popularity for its free availability and MARC21/OPAC support. Other studies also confirmed that automation software improves library services, reduces staff workload, and enhances remote access for users.

The third objective focused on the challenges faced by medical libraries in Punjab while implementing automation software. The results indicated that libraries encountered several issues, including insufficient budgets, lack of financial resources, inadequate upgrading facilities, poor internet connectivity, non-cooperation from parent institutions, and limited access to training. These findings are consistent with Hudron Kari and Emmanuel Baro (2014), who reported similar problems such as acceptance confusion, lack of expertise, unreliable power supply, poor ICT infrastructure, and insufficient funding. Komolafe-Opadeji and Ojo (2019) also confirmed that university libraries face obstacles such as low internet bandwidth, financial limitations, and high ILS maintenance costs. Jasimudeen et al. (2012) reported that Koha faced adoption challenges in India due to networking issues and administrative delays. Similarly, Shafi Ullah and Qutab (2012) identified barriers such as lack of interest from technical groups, librarians' reluctance to adopt new technologies, and financial constraints. Other scholars (Ajani & Buraimo, 2022; Alam, 2017; Yadav & Rajput, 2022; Otunla, 2016; Rajput & Gautam, 2010) also highlighted challenges including inadequate expertise, poor infrastructure, insufficient funding, lack of training, technophobia, and limited institutional support.

The present study also evaluate satisfaction levels with the features of library automation software. The findings showed that respondents were generally satisfied with various modules and functionalities. High satisfaction was reported with cataloguing, circulation, acquisition, administration, and patron modules, as well as ease of use, multilingual features, online help, customization, maintenance, and reporting functions. Respondents also expressed satisfaction with web OPAC, data migration to newer versions, ILL facilities, backup systems, new arrivals display, and social media integration. These findings align with Ahammad (2014), who concluded that Koha meets the automation needs of libraries. Alam and Islam (2021) reported user satisfaction due to advanced features such as OPAC, self-checkout, and automated alerts. Khan

and Aysha (2021) further confirmed satisfaction with features like circulation, administration, web OPAC, and ILL. Similarly, Asim and Mairaj (2019) highlighted high satisfaction among professionals with Koha's cataloguing, circulation, and OPAC modules.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The primary aim of this survey-based research was to investigate the extent of adoption and use of library automation software, to identify the challenges encountered during its implementation, and to evaluate the satisfaction levels of medical libraries in Punjab with regard to the features of such systems. The findings revealed that the majority of medical institute, college, and university libraries in Punjab were fully automated. A considerable proportion of these libraries had adopted free and open-source software, with Koha and LIMS emerging as the most widely utilized systems. Thirteen evaluative statements were presented to determine the purposes of adopting library automation software. The results indicated that medical libraries primarily implemented automation systems to facilitate the execution of routine library operations. Key reasons for adoption included the software's strong reputation within the professional community, its multilingual support, cost-free accessibility, availability of essential features, and the provision of Web OPAC. Furthermore, respondents confirmed that automation software supports MARC21 standards for cataloguing and enables copy cataloguing through Z39.50. These findings underscore the importance of automation software in enabling libraries to fully leverage advanced features and services. By automating cataloguing, circulation, and resource management functions, medical libraries are better positioned to address the educational and research needs of students, researchers, and healthcare professionals. Importantly, the findings may also serve as a practical checklist for libraries in the process of selecting automation systems, while offering useful insights for software designers and developers to integrate these essential features into future solutions. Despite the advantages, the study

revealed that medical libraries continue to face several obstacles in the effective utilization of automation software. These challenges include inadequate budgets, limited internet connectivity, insufficient training opportunities, and lack of institutional cooperation. Other difficulties reported were the absence of system upgrade facilities, a shortage of consultancy and technical support, and restricted administrative rights, often controlled by parent institutional IT departments. With regard to satisfaction levels, the findings indicate that medical libraries in Punjab are generally content with the performance of automation software. The highest levels of satisfaction were reported for circulation modules, cataloguing modules, and overall ease of use. Respondents also expressed satisfaction with patron management modules, ease of installation, affordability, Web OPAC, social media integration, backup facilities, display of new arrivals, interlibrary loan (ILL) services, data migration to updated versions, report generation, and administrative modules. Collectively, these findings suggest that medical libraries in Punjab are broadly satisfied with the functioning and performance of their adopted automation systems. In conclusion, this study highlights that the selection of library automation software must be guided by the availability of core features such as cataloguing, circulation, Web OPAC, multilingual support, and user-friendliness. These elements are critical to ensuring that automation systems not only enhance library services but also support users effectively and improve the overall efficiency of library operations. This study recommends that prior to investment, libraries should ensure that the software includes essential features, such as reliability, security, an intuitive user interface, Web OPAC capability, advanced search functionalities, compliance with international standards (e.g., RDA, UNIMARC, MARC21), and scalability for future upgrades. Orientation sessions and workshops should be organized to encourage maximum utilization of available software features and facilities. Medical colleges, universities, and institutes should allocate sufficient funding for the implementation and maintenance of library automation systems.

Limitations, Delimitations and Future Suggestions

Findings are based primarily on self-reported data, which may be subject to bias. Further studies employing mixed methods could provide deeper insights. Limited access to updated records, combined with the lack of cooperation from some libraries, may have affected the comprehensiveness of the data. The study focused exclusively on medical libraries in Punjab; hence, findings may not be generalizable to libraries in other provinces or countries. Input was limited to library professionals, without incorporating perspectives from students, faculty, or healthcare practitioners. For future suggestions, the current study is based on the use of library software for automation; a further study investigates the impact of automation on information retrieval in medical libraries. Explore the mobile access and remote services through library automation in medical libraries. To explore the cyber security challenges in automated medical library software

Theoretical and Practical Implications

The study contributes to the theoretical understanding of library automation by demonstrating its potential to enhance information retrieval through improved accuracy and recall of search results. By leveraging automation systems, medical libraries can facilitate quick and targeted access to complex medical knowledge resources. Practically, the study reveals that library automation significantly reduces manual workload in areas such as cataloguing, circulation, and acquisitions, leading to increased operational efficiency. It enhances user access to digital medical resources and supports interlibrary collaboration through ILL systems. Automation also ensures 24/7 availability of digital collections and strengthens data security through improved backup and recovery protocols. These findings offer actionable guidance for library administrators and policymakers in the selection, implementation, or enhancement of automation systems in medical libraries.

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